

Factors Influencing Employee Performance

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Abstract:- Purpose — This study aims to examine the role of work engagement in mediating the influence of competence and work environment on performance.

Design/methodology/approach — The sample in this study was determined using a census study population technique, so that 53 observations were obtained from 4 villages in Situbondo District. The analysis technique used in this study is path analysis using SPSS 25.

Findings — Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the performance of village apparatus is directly positive and significantly influenced by competence, work engagement, and work environment. In addition, it was found that competence and work environment had a significant positive effect on performance through work engagement.

Recommendation — This research is still far from perfect, so future research needs to be perfected. Future research can deepen the influence of horizontal education mismatch on work engagement and village apparatus performance in order to improve the findings of this study. In addition, future research is expected to be able to examine a larger number of samples so that the findings are more representative of conditions in the field.

Keywords:- Earning Management, Financial Performance, Jakarta Islamic Index.

I. INTRODUCTION

The reform era and globalization competition are driving factors for the acceleration of changes in the performance of government officials in a better direction (Ilhama, 2020). This causes demands for government officials to be able to carry out their duties in a professional, moral, clean and ethical manner. Bureaucratic efforts and improving the performance of the apparatus are expected to be able to support the success of the national development program. According to Ilhama (2020), in order to achieve the success of national development goals, the participation of Civil Servants (PNS) is needed as elements of the state apparatus, servants of the state and servants of the community who play the role of executors of government activities and development tasks.

The application of the current decentralization principle has brought changes and updates to the village development system. Currently, the pattern or line of thought for village development has gone from top down to bottom up, from technocratic to participatory approaches, from empowerment models with material capital to social capital empowerment, from growth orientation to social justice. Efforts to implement a new paradigm in village development have gained formal legitimacy and strength since the Government of the Republic of Indonesia ratified and issued Village Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages. The ratification of this law is a form

of acknowledgment as well as the state's attention to the existence of villages. Through this law, the current existence of the village is not as an object of development, but instead as a subject that has legal independence and authority in regulating all its affairs. This is in accordance with the provisions of Article 1 paragraph 1 of the Village Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages which emphasizes that a village is a legal community unit that has territorial boundaries that are authorized to regulate and manage government affairs, local community interests based on community initiatives, and original rights. -suggestions that are recognized and respected.

According to Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, Village Government is the implementation of government affairs and the interests of the local community within the system of government of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The parties mandated to carry out the functions of village administration are the Village Administration and the BPD. Village Government is the Village Head or what is referred to by another name assisted by Village apparatus as an element of Village Administration. To be able to fulfill and carry out its duties, the Village Government has 4 (four) areas of Village Authority, ; 1) Implementation of Village Administration, 2) Village Development Implementation, 3) Village Community Development, 4) Village Community Empowerment.

Carrying out its authority functions, one of the important elements that urgently needs to be prepared immediately in relation to the implementation of village autonomy is village government officials who have sufficient ability or competence to encourage increased government performance which so far seems relatively low (Junaedy Pandey et al 2015). The importance of having the ability or competence of village government officials because adequate village government officials can determine the success of the village in carrying out improvements in the fields of governance, development, coaching and community empowerment (Aminah & Sutanto, 2018). From this it can be seen that the village government apparatus determines the success of a village in making improvements in the fields of government, development, guidance and empowerment of the community, so that having village government officials who have the ability and competence is an important thing.

However, in reality, the performance of government apparatus, especially the performance of village government apparatus in Bondowoso, is still relatively low. The relatively low performance evaluation of village officials has also become a concern of the Minister for Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform, Tjahjo Kumolo, who reminded that consistency in service quality is needed (Warta Ekonomi, 12 March 2022). Meanwhile, according to Lumempow, et al.

(2021) states that the performance of village officials that the community often complains about is one of them in the form of a lack of service quality. So that it can be understood that one indicator of the low performance of the village government apparatus can be indicated by the many demands and complaints from the community regarding the quality of services provided, such as the processing of residence documents, land certificates, birth certificates and others such as village officials not knowing their job descriptions which resulted in the centralization of tasks to the Village Secretary only, as well as discipline in setting working hours for the Village Government which is still low. This condition applies to almost all villages in the Situbondo District as the location of this research. From the existing data as of 31 December 2020 to 2021 regarding the Summary of Village Apparatus Performance Evaluation, an evaluation value was obtained with an average of below 70%. This is of course influenced by many factors, including the abilities or competencies possessed by the village government officials themselves, such as the level of formal education, training/skills or non-formal education, experience in carrying out tasks and evaluation of the performance of village government officials which are not routinely carried out. These things are factors that also determine the extent of competence of the village government officials themselves.

Competence is very influential in the performance of village government officials. The concept of competency is not new to American organizational psychology in particular. The competency movement has emerged since the late 1960s and early 1970s. The term competency as a translation from English competency has a simple meaning, an ability or skill (Wojowasito and Poerwadar Minta, 1980). In subsequent interpretations, among experts or writers there are many differences in interpreting or defining this word competence, depending on the perspective or approach of each. As previously mentioned, competence is knowledge and skills that can be acquired through learning (education), training, and experience. The same thing was also stated by Megginson, Matthews and Banfield (1993), using expressions such as competency and capability to describe goals and learning; to become competent in their field or have the capability to carry out their work.

In addition to competence, the work environment is also considered important. Agencies that have a good and comfortable work environment will provide motivation for their employees to improve their performance. In addition, good working conditions will help reduce boredom and fatigue. So it is expected to improve performance. According to Nitsemto (2004:66), "The work environment is something that exists around the workers and can influence him in carrying out the tasks he is charged with". Agencies must be able to pay attention to the conditions that exist in the organization both inside and outside the workplace, so that employees can work smoothly and feel safe. According to Sedarmayanti (2001), working environment conditions are said to be good or appropriate if humans can carry out activities optimally, healthy, safe and comfortable. The suitability of the work environment can be seen as a result in the long term, furthermore unfavorable work environments

can demand more labor and time and do not support the creation of an efficient work system design. From a physical perspective, the working environment of village government officials in the village office in the working area of Situbondo District, Situbondo has almost the same building characteristics, where there is a meeting hall in the middle of the village office area, partitions between rooms that separate the village head's room from other village apparatus rooms and judging from the size of the village apparatus workspace which is not too large. In terms of structuring the environmental conditions of the village office, it is rare to find parks in the village office area. For non-physical conditions that can be seen from the working relationship between the village head and existing village officials, there are several problems that occur. There was disharmony between the village head and village apparatus which ended in the dismissal or resignation of the village apparatus and the occurrence of legal cases which resulted in the dismissal of the village head by the Regent for being involved in a criminal act.

Thus, with improving the performance of village government apparatus is influenced by competency factors and the work environment which is mediated by work engagement. According to the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) and Colonial Life, there are several other work facilities that the majority of job seekers are looking for, starting from non-salary work facilities to a working atmosphere, which in the realm of organizational industrial psychology is known as work engagement. Bakker, et al. (2006) in Astuti, et al. (2016) stated that work engagement is a form of engagement which is interpreted as a positive, satisfying and work-related mental state which is characterized by three aspects, strength, dedication and devotion. It was further stated that by having work engagement, a person will tend to be more productive, creative and willing to work more. In the context of village government apparatus, village officials who are local villagers from a distance and psychologically can be judged as the closest people to the circle of power in the village government, both from a political aspect and from a close kinship aspect. Village officials who are expected to carry out their role as community servants, must have a feeling of being involved with their work, so that the work carried out is not a burden and produces an optimal performance.

Research on the influence of competence, work environment and work engagement on performance has been carried out by several previous researchers. The results of research conducted by Faizal, et al. (2018) shows that work competence can support performance results. Research conducted by Elizar and Tanjung (2018) also shows the same thing, it is proven that competence has a positive and significant influence on performance. Another study, conducted by Nurmashita, et al. (2013) also showed a similar thing, that is, employee competence has a significant influence on the quality of service provided by these employees.

The research results of I Wayan Arta Artana (2012: 78) prove that the work environment ranks first or has a dominant influence on employee performance. This indicates that a comfortable and conducive work environment greatly

influences the performance of village officials. According to Leea & Brand (2005) in Kusendi and Ispurwanto's (2017) study, the relationship between the work environment and work engagement has a positive and significant relationship. Based on this research, it was found that the better the quality of the employee's work environment in supporting his creative performance, the higher his sense of attachment to the company. Meyer's research (2012) revealed that a positive driving factor for work engagement is a factor of harmonious relations with colleagues, with superiors and subordinates in the company. Based on the results of observations, it is known that the villages in the Situbondo sub-district are villages that have conducted measurable performance evaluations based on the guide format from the East Java provincial government. In addition, the Situbondo sub-district is classified as a strategic area compared to other sub-districts located in remote areas, so it is predicted that the village apparatus in this sub-district is more competent. Several of these basic reasons contributed to the selection of villages in this sub-district as research objects..

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Theory Review

➤ Job Competence

Competence is a mixture of skills, knowledge, attitudes and other personal characteristics that are needed to achieve success in a job, which is measured using agreed standards, and can be improved through training and development (Marwansyah, 2016). According to the Decree of the Head of the State Civil Service Agency Number 46A of 2003 dated November 21, 2003, the meaning of competence is the ability in the form of knowledge, skills and attitudes that must be possessed by Civil Servants in carrying out their duties. Dessler (2006) defines competency as a characteristic of a person that can be shown, which includes knowledge, skills, and behavior, which can result in performance and achievement. Watson Wyatt (in Noor Fuad, 2009), defines competency as a combination of skills, knowledge, and attitude. These skills, knowledge, and behaviors can be observed and critically applied to the success of an organization and the work performance and personal contribution of employees to their organization. McClelland (1973) defines competence as a fundamental characteristic possessed by a person that has a direct influence on, or can predict, excellent performance.

➤ Work Environment

The work environment is synonymous with a work atmosphere which plays a big role in encouraging the active participation of employees in completing their duties (Hastuti, 2021). According to Omari et. al. (2019), the environment is everything that relates to employees and is able to influence employee performance. Several studies classify the work environment as unhealthy (toxic) and conducive (Akinyele, 2010; Chaddha, Pandey and Noida, 2011; Yusuf and Metiboba, 2012; Assaf and Alswalha, 2013). Izzah et. al. (2020) stated that the work environment can be grouped into two, the non-physical work environment and the physical work environment. The non-physical work environment is all

conditions related to the working relationship between employees and superiors and co-workers (Sedarmayanti, 2011). The non-physical work environment can affect employee performance (Izzah et al., 2020) when the situation at work is conducive, colleagues are easy to work with and the relationship with superiors is good, employees will enjoy their work so that their performance is more optimal. The physical work environment according to Sedarmayanti (2011) is all the physical conditions found around the workplace that can affect employees either directly or indirectly. McGuire and McLaren (2007) argue that the physical environment of an organization, especially its layout and design, can influence employee behavior at work. Work Engagement as a condition in which a person is able to commit to the organization both emotionally and intellectually. The dimensions of work engagement include: (1) Talking positively about the organization to colleagues and referring the organization to employees and potential customers; (2) Have a strong desire to become a member of the organization, even though there is an opportunity to work elsewhere; (3) Giving effort and showing tough behavior to contribute to the success of the organization. Engagement is a complex concept and is influenced by many factors, including workplace culture, organizational communication, managerial style that triggers trust and respect as well as the leadership adopted and the reputation of the organization itself.

➤ Employee Performance

Mangkunegara (2009) defines performance as a form of work results achieved by an employee in quality and quantity in accordance with the responsibilities given. Achmad Amin (2009) says that performance is basically determined by three things, namely competence, desire and work environment. In other words, it can be said that performance is the result of both quantity and quality work achieved by someone in carrying out the tasks for which they are responsible. Human resource performance is work performance or work results (output) both in quality and quantity achieved by the HR unit in carrying out work tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given to them (Izzah et al. 2019). Performance can also be in the form of actions or implementation of tasks that have been completed by someone within a certain time and can be measured. From several expert opinions it can be concluded that the definition of an employee's performance is the result of work quantitatively or qualitatively, creativity, flexibility, reliability or other things desired by the organization.

B. Hypotheses Development

Spencer (1993), Mulyasa (2004); Hutapea (2008) states that work competence is a basic characteristic of a person consisting of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that have a causal relationship with work performance or extraordinary work effectiveness. Wibowo (2007) argues that: work competence is an ability to carry out or perform a job or task based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required by the job. Work competence is an individual characteristic that contributes to a person's success in completing work (Sjahrazad et al., 2009). Meanwhile, according to Boulter et al. (2003) competency is a characteristic that allows someone to perform very well.

Spencer & Spencer (1993) also put forward competence as a characteristic of a person that directly influences his performance at work. More assertively said by Sujana (2012), the higher the competency the higher the performance.

A number of research results prove that there is a significant positive effect of work competence on individual performance, Setyaningtyas et al. (2013), Lotunani et al. (2014), Renyut et al. (2017), Mukhtar (2018), Mahmood et al. (2018), Sari and Lestari (2018), Keerthy and Biyu (2018), Suriadi et al. (2018), Suhardi and Sari (2018), Zhang et al. (2018), Berliana et al. (2018), Rabo (2018), and Martini et al. (2018). In addition, the results of research by Pandei et al. (2012) concluded that employees have the perception that their knowledge can improve performance or productivity. Dhermawan et al. (2012) which showed that competency significantly influences work performance in employees of the Bali Province Public Works Office who are respondents. Based on the results of this study, the research hypothesis is stated as follows:

H₁ : work competence affects the performance of village government apparatus.

➤ *The Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance*

According to Doelhadi (2001), a good environment greatly influences employee performance when working. Environment pleasant work conditions, such as clean office conditions, adequate lighting, adequate ventilation, harmonious relations between employees, good leadership, etc., will lead to feelings of satisfaction in employees, so that employees will feel at home and enthusiastic about completing work. Vice versa, a bad work environment causes employees to feel uncomfortable at work so that it can affect the resulting performance.

According to the results of Putra and Suharnomo's research (2012) the work environment influences the performance of employees of the Java Province Education and Training Agency. The results of this study are in line with Purnomo's research (2007) at the Forestry and Plantation Service of Jepara Regency, which results that leadership, motivation and work environment have a significant effect on the performance of Civil Servants in the Jepara Regency Forestry and Plantation Service. Based on the explanation above, the hypothesis taken is:

H₂: work environment influences the performance of village government apparatus in Situbondo District

➤ *The Effect of Work Engagement on Employee Performance*

Schaufeli et al. (2002) emphasized that workers who have a high level of engagement will have a high emotional attachment to their company so that it will affect the completion of work and tend to have satisfactory work quality. Employees who are engaged will be motivated to improve their performance and productivity, willing to accept challenges, and feel that their work gives meaning to them. Workers who have work engagement with their jobs have many advantages, being able to maintain and increase work

productivity because they feel happy working for the company.

Wardani and Fatimah's research (2020) found that the Intellectual Competence dimension has the greatest influence on work engagement. This study found that workers with horizontal education mismatch had low competence, but even though the competence of workers was low, they showed moderate and high work engagement. This is in line with previous research conducted by Akkermans, Schaufeli, Brenninkmeijer, and Blonk (2013) which found that career competence has an influence on work engagement. In addition, career competence is a partial mediator in the relationship between work resources and work engagement. Based on the explanation above, the hypothesis taken is:

H₃: work engagement affects the performance of village government officials in Situbondo District

III. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Research

This type of research is a quantitative research with the method of path analysis (path analysis), where in this study the aim is to determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable directly or indirectly. In this study, we wanted to determine the effect of competence and environment on performance through work engagement with village officials in the Situbondo sub-district, Situbondo.

B. Types and sources of data

The types and sources of data used in this study are primary and secondary data. According to Sujarweni (2015: 89) "Primary data is data obtained from respondents through questionnaires, focus groups, and panels, or also data from interviews with researchers with informants. The data obtained from this primary data must be processed again. Data sources that directly provide data for data collection. The primary data in this study were questionnaires that had been filled out by village officials in Situbondo District, Situbondo Regency as respondents. While secondary data is defined as data obtained from records, books, and magazines in the form of published company financial reports, government reports, articles, books as theory, magazines, and so on. Secondary data in this study is data in the form of reports from the Village Government sent to related agencies, the Community and Village Empowerment Office of Situbondo. The data collection method in this study was carried out by observation by direct observation of the research object (respondents) and questionnaires, the data collection method by providing a number of written questions in a structured manner to research respondents related to the responses of various research variables in this study which consisted of from work competence, work environment, performance and work engagement. Research population and samples.

Population according to Sugiyono (2017: 80) "Population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to study and then draw conclusions". In addition, according to Sujarweni (2015: 80) "Population is the

total number consisting of objects or subjects that have certain characteristics and qualities determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn." From this understanding it can be obtained an understanding that the population is the whole object or subject that has the characteristics or criteria that have been determined by the researcher. The sample, according to Sugiyono (2017: 81) "The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population". Another understanding states that the sample is part of the population that represents the population to be taken (Notoatmojo, 2005). In this study, the objects of research were all village officials in the working area of Talkandang Village, Olean Village, Kotakan Village and Kalibagor Village which are included in the auspices of Situbondo District, Situbondo Regency, totaling 44 village officials. So that the sampling technique to be used is total sampling because the number of existing research objects is less than 100. Total sampling is the number of samples is equal to the population (Sugiyono,

2007). Furthermore, Sugiyono (2007) states that the total population is less than 100, the entire population can be used as a sample for previous research.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Instrumen Test

➤ *Validity Test*

The validity test is intended to determine how much accuracy and accuracy a measuring instrument has in carrying out its measuring function. Validity test as a measuring tool in this study, using Pearson's product moment correlation, by correlating each question with a total score, then the results of the correlation are compared with the critical number of a significant level of 5% (Prayitno, 2010: 90). Following in Table 1, the results of validity testing:

Tabel 1 Validity Test

Variabel	Product Moment Pearson's	Sig.		a	description
X1.1	0,87	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
X1.2	0,81	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
X1.3	0,83	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
X1.4	0,81	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
X2.1	0,84	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
X2.2	0,86	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
X2.3	0,76	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
X1.4	0,83	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
X1.5	0,70	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Z1	0,86	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Z2	0,86	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Z3	0,80	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Z4	0,89	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Y1	0,76	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Y2	0,72	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Y3	0,66	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Y4	0,82	0,000	<	0,05	Valid
Y5	0,83	0,000	<	0,05	Valid

Source : Lampiran 3

Based on table 1, it is known that each indicator (item) in the variables used has a Pearson's product moment value with a significance of 0.000 <0.05, so that the indicators (items) used in this research variable can be declared relevant and can be used as a tool in data collection. Uji Reliabilitas.

This test is carried out to show the extent to which a measurement result is relatively consistent. A good question or statement is a clear question or statement that is easy to understand and has the same interpretation even though it is delivered to different respondents and at different times. The reliability test was carried out using Cronbach's alpha. An instrument is said to be reliable if Cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.60 (Prayitno, 2010:97). In Table 2, the results of the reliability test are presented:

Table 2 Hasil Uji Reliabilitas.

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Cut off	N of Item	description
X1	0,863	> 0,6	4	Reliable
X2	0,840	> 0,6	5	Reliable
Z	0,882	> 0,6	4	Reliable
Y	0,824	> 0,6	5	Reliable

Based on Table 2, the reliability test results above show that the data obtained is reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha values are 0.863, 0.840, 0.882, and 0.824 > 0.60, so the data obtained can be declared reliable or feasible as a tool in data collection. Uji Asumsi Klasik

The classic assumption test consists of 3 types of tests, normality, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity tests. Based on the results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov one-sample method, it can be seen that the probability or significance values for each variable are 0.243, 0.566, 0.255, and 0.132 > 0.05, so it can be stated that the data in this study are normally distributed. While the results of the multicollinearity test show that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables because it shows a VIF value of less than 10. Also the results of the heteroscedasticity test show that there is no heteroscedasticity. because the data scatter does not form a certain line or there is no clear pattern. as well as the points spread above and below zero on the Y.

B. Path Analysis

After going through the instrument test phase and the assumptions of the feasibility of the regression model. Then the path analysis is carried out. The path analysis carried out in this study relates to the analysis of the dependence of a dependent variable on one or more independent or intervening variables with the aim of knowing how much influence the independent or intervening variables have on the dependent variable. The results of the path analysis between the independent variables, work competence and the intervening variable work engagement. as well as the dependent variable is performance of the apparatus. The results of the path analysis in this study are presented in table 3 as follows:

Table 3. Value of R²

Standardized		t test		ttable	Sig.		a	description
Path	Beta (β)							
X1 → Y	0.331	3.746	>	1.674	0.001	<	0.05	significant
X2 → Y	0.662	7.488	>	1.674	0.000	<	0.05	significant
X3 → Y	0.819	9.479	>	1.674	0.000	<	0.05	significant
ε1	0.447	-		-	-		-	-
ε2	0.398	-		-	-		-	-

The results of the direct effect data analysis show that all independent variables have a significant positive effect on the performance of village officials. Based on the path coefficient values presented in table 3, mathematically it can be presented as follows:

Apparatus Performance (Y) = 0.373 + 0.331 X1 + 0.662 X2 + 0.819 X3 + 0.398 + ε1

C. Discussion

1) The effect of Competence on Employee Performance

The results of the direct effect data analysis show that there is a significant influence of work competency variables on the performance variables of village apparatus in Situbondo District. Based on these results, it can be explained that increasing work competence can bring positive changes to the performance of village apparatus and vice versa. The results of the research hypothesis test support research conducted by Pokatong et al., (2015) which states that competency has a significant effect on employees. The findings of this study also confirm that the research results are in line with research conducted by Rande, (2017) and Rahmawati, (2019) which state that competence has a significant effect on employee performance. Organizations with knowledge-based human resources are considered to have the ability to compete in the future (Harjanti, 2009). The comparative advantage paradigm which concentrates strength on a large and cheap labor force is currently considered irrelevant in the face of globalization. Conversely, comparative advantage that relies on skills is a demand for today's organizational needs, because the quality of goods, services and services will depend heavily on the human resources in it (Surya Dharma, Usahawan XXVII, 1998:20). Individual ability to achieve performance success requires internal encouragement, one of which is the ability/competence of the individual itself. Bacal (2002: 149)

provides examples of individual factors that can improve the achievement of HR performance including the level of motivation, commitment, expertise, knowledge, skills, and thinking ability. This statement indicates that performance is always related to human resources who are directly involved in their performance. Therefore, human resources need to receive support that can be raised from a situation both internal and external to the individual.

Quality human resources are the demands of organizations today both in the private sector and in the government (public) sector, while to get quality human resources it is necessary to pay attention to the necessary Human Resources planning processes. Motivation as a process of giving encouragement is a series of activities that must be carried out or carried out to encourage employees to have goals that are in line with the organization. Employee awareness of the situation that is expected to occur is that at this time they can actually try even harder to increase their capacity or ability from the current condition to a maximum condition.

2) The effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing have proven that there is an influence of the work environment on the performance of village apparatus in Situbondo District. Based on the results of the path analysis, it was found that the sig value of the work environment on the performance of village officials was 0.000 < 0.05 with a regression coefficient of 0.331. These results indicate that there is a significant positive influence of work environment variables on the performance of village officials. The results of this study provide empirical evidence that the performance quality of village apparatus in Situbondo District is directly proportional to their work environment. According to (Sedarmayanti, 2011) individuals in companies or

organizations with a conducive work environment tend to have more performance capable of achieving optimal results. This statement is supported by Weol (2015) which states that a conducive work environment will encourage employees to work harder. This is because employees who already know their duties and responsibilities well will try to achieve a high level of work morale. Conducive working environment conditions will affect the successful achievement of these duties and responsibilities.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Pratama and Wismarein (2018) that the work environment is proven to have a positive and significant influence on employee performance. Furthermore, research conducted by Wijaya and Susanty (2017), Budianto and Katini (2015), the results of their research can be seen that there is a high positive relationship between the work environment and employee performance. According to Budiarto and Katini (2015) the work environment is a measurement tool that will affect employee performance if the work environment in an institution is good. A pleasant work environment for employees through increased harmonious relations with superiors, colleagues and subordinates, as well as support from adequate facilities and infrastructure in the workplace will have a positive impact on employees so that employee performance can increase. This is in accordance with the opinion of Sedarmayanti (2011) that an employee is predicted to be able to achieve optimal performance results, if supported by an appropriate working environment condition. The results of this study concluded that the more conducive the work environment in the company, the better the performance of employees, and conversely an inadequate work environment will reduce employee performance. The better the work environment that exists in the company, it will improve employee performance. The existence of a good and supportive work environment will make employees comfortable at work, therefore companies must pay more attention to the work environment in the company in order to improve the environment that is positive, comfortable, safe, fun and can be conducive and feel enthusiastic about carrying out their duties, so that will improve employee performance.

3) *The effect of Work Engagement on Employee Performance*

The results of the path analysis in this study provide empirical evidence that there is a significant positive effect of the work engagement variable on the performance of village apparatus in Situbondo District. The findings of this study support the results of research by Carter et al., (2018), Christian et al., (2011), Kim et al., (2013), Ibrahim and Al Falasi, (2014) which found a positive and significant correlation between engagement employees and employee performance, as well as employee engagement can be used as a performance predictor. According to Bakker and Bal (2010), work engagement is a form of enthusiasm and energy invested by employees in their work so that these employees are able to achieve optimal performance.

According to Ismail et al., (2018), when employees are satisfied with their experiences at work, these employees tend to be motivated to show their creativity and commitment. Employees who value work and find it meaningful are more likely to invest additional effort to achieve more than what the company requires. Hon (2012) defines this phenomenon as the creative performance shown by employees. Based on this explanation, it can be concluded that organizations need to foster a pleasant atmosphere in the workplace to encourage high involvement and creativity. Employees who are highly engaged in their work focus their energies on productive ideas on the job in the first stage, which in turn serves to increase job performance (Ismail et al., 2018). In addition, Marciano (2010) explained that work engagement can increase worker productivity, lower turnover, increase efficiency within the company, reduce fraud that occurs in the work environment. In fact, work engagement can increase customer satisfaction, besides that, work engagement will have the effect of reducing worker absenteeism, decreasing worker complaints against the company, and working accidents in the company will also decrease (Akbar, 2013). This statement can be interpreted that work engagement is an important thing that must be owned by an employee so that employees have good work performance (Sriwidodo & Haryanto, 2010; Piartrini, 2011; Tahir, 2013, Rachmawati, 2016). The importance of work engagement has been recognized by management (Deloitte Consulting LLP and Bersin, 2014). Until now, work engagement is one of the hot topics for discussion between consulting firms and well-known business media (Saks, 2006). Work engagement has become a widespread and popular term (Robinson, Perryman & Hayday, 2004). Wah (1999) and Sakovska (2012) state that work engagement is one of the five challenges in human resource management.

V. CONCLUSION

This study aims to examine the effect of competence, work environment and work engagement on the performance of village officials in Situbondo District. The results of the path analysis provide empirical evidence that all independent variables have a significant positive effect on the performance of village officials. This study provides empirical evidence that work competence and work engagement work environment have a significant positive effect on the performance of village officials. Therefore, this study recommends that the village government always improve employee competence and also improve office facilities and infrastructure so that it can trigger increased work engagement and performance. This research is still far from perfect, so future research needs to be perfected. Future research can deepen the influence of horizontal education mismatch on work engagement and village apparatus performance in order to improve the findings of this study. In addition, future research is expected to be able to examine a larger number of samples so that the findings are more representative of conditions in the field.

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